

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN CALLING AND APPEALING

Alibayeva N

f.f.f.d (Phd)

Toshtemirova Xosiyat

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Abstract. This article gives the difference between calling and appealing in texts. Let's define what each word means. Appeal is a verb that means to make a request for something. Call, on the other hand, can be used as a verb or a noun. As a verb, it means to shout or cry out. As a noun, it can refer to a phone call or a visit.

Keywords: calling, appealing, connotations, proper word, request.

РАЗНИЦА МЕЖДУ ПРИЗЫВОМ И АПЕЛЛЯЦИЕЙ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассмотрена разница между призывом и обращением в текстах. Давайте определимся, что означает каждое слово. Обращение — глагол, означающий обращение к чему-либо. Call, с другой стороны, может использоваться как глагол или существительное. Глагол означает кричать или кричать. Как существительное, оно может относиться к телефонному звонку или визиту.

Ключевые слова: призыв, обращение, коннотации, слово собственное, просьба.

Let's define what each word means. Appeal is a verb that means to make a request for something. Call, on the other hand, can be used as a verb or a noun. As a verb, it means to shout or cry out. As a noun, it can refer to a phone call or a visit.

When it comes to choosing between the words “appeal” and “call,” context plays a crucial role in determining which word is appropriate. Both words can be used to persuade or convince someone, but they have slightly different connotations that can impact their effectiveness depending on the situation. So, which of these words is the proper word to use? The answer is, it depends on the context. If you're making a request or plea for something, then appeal is the right word to use. On the other hand, if you're shouting or crying out, or referring to a phone call or visit, then call is the appropriate word.

In the following sections, we'll explore each of these words in more detail and provide examples of how to use them correctly.

Define Appeal

Appeal is a term used to describe the act of making a request or an appeal to someone in order to gain their support, approval, or agreement. It can also refer to the quality of something that makes it attractive or interesting to a particular audience or group of people.

Appeal can take many forms, including emotional, logical, and ethical appeals. Emotional appeals aim to evoke strong feelings in the reader or listener, while logical appeals rely on facts and evidence to support a particular argument. Ethical appeals appeal to the reader or listener's sense of morality or right and wrong. In marketing and advertising, appeal is often used to describe the way in which a product or service is marketed to consumers. Advertisers may use emotional appeals to create a sense of desire or urgency in the consumer, or they may use logical appeals to demonstrate the benefits or advantages of a particular product or service.

Define Call

Call is a term that can refer to a number of different things, depending on the context in which it is used. In general, however, call refers to the act of making a request or demand for something. In business, a call can refer to a sales call, in which a salesperson attempts to sell a product or service to a potential customer. It can also refer to a conference call, in which multiple people are connected via telephone or video conference to discuss a particular topic or issue

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So, which of these words is the proper word to use? The answer is, it depends on the context. If you're making a request or plea for something, then appeal is the right word to use. On the other hand, if you're shouting or crying out, or referring to a phone call or visit, then call is the appropriate word. In a more general sense, call can also refer to the act of making a request or demand for something, such as when a person calls for help in an emergency situation.

Call can also be used in a more abstract sense, such as when a person feels a calling to a particular profession or vocation. In this sense, call refers to a sense of purpose or direction that a person feels in their life

How To Properly Use The Words In A Sentence

Using the right words in a sentence is crucial to convey the intended message effectively. In this section, we will discuss how to use the words "appeal" and "call" in a sentence.

How To Use "Appeal" In A Sentence

The word "appeal" can be used in different contexts, but it generally means to attract or interest someone, or to make a request for help or support. Here are some examples of how to use "appeal" in a sentence:

- The new product design is expected to appeal to younger consumers.
- The charity is making an appeal for donations to help the homeless.
- The defendant plans to appeal the court's decision.

In these examples, "appeal" is used to describe the act of attracting or requesting support or help. It is important to note that "appeal" can also be used as a noun to describe the quality of being attractive or interesting, or the act of making a request for help or support

How To Use "Call" In A Sentence

The word "call" can also be used in different ways, but it generally means to communicate with someone or to make a request or demand. Here are some examples of how to use "call" in a sentence: I need to call my friend to confirm our plans for tonight.

- The boss called a meeting to discuss the new project.
- The customer called to complain about the service.

In these examples, "call" is used to describe the act of communicating or making a request or demand. It is important to note that "call" can also be used as a noun to describe the act of making a request or demand, or a decision made by an official or organization. In order to further understand the difference between "appeal" and "call", it is helpful to examine examples of how they are used in sentences. Here are some examples:

Sentence:

The advertisement for the new car model had a strong emotional appeal to young drivers.

The charity organization made an appeal for donations to help those affected by the natural disaster.

The lawyer made an appeal to the jury to consider the defendant's difficult upbringing in their decision.

The company's marketing campaign had a broad appeal to consumers of all ages.

The book's author used vivid descriptions to appeal to readers' senses and emotions.

The restaurant's menu had a wide appeal due to its diverse range of dishes.

The politician's speech had a strong appeal to voters who were concerned about economic issues.

The fashion designer's new collection had a strong appeal to those who appreciate bold and unconventional styles.

The movie's plot had a universal appeal that resonated with audiences around the world.

The salesperson's persuasive appeal convinced the customer to make a purchase.

Examples Of Using "Call" In A Sentence:

The coach called a timeout to discuss strategy with the team.

The teacher called on the student to answer the question.

The police officer called for backup when the situation became dangerous.

The company's CEO called a meeting to discuss the new merger.

The doctor called in a specialist to consult on the patient's condition.

The restaurant called to confirm the reservation for the large party.

Finally, some people use both words interchangeably, without realizing that they have different meanings. This can lead to confusion or miscommunication, especially in written communication where tone and context can be harder to convey. To avoid this mistake, it's important to understand the differences between the two words and to choose the one that best fits the tone and context of your message.

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